

VASOACTIVE INTESTINAL PEPTIDE AS A DIAGNOSTIC OR PROGNOSTIC BIOMARKER IN MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW PROTOCOL

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This an original research protocol. This protocol is a modification of the template created by Cruz-Martínez, R. R. (2024). *Template for a Systematic Literature Review Protocol (2.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13331159>, and follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) guidelines.

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1. Background

Biomarkers have emerged as a highly efficacious and minimally invasive solution to meet the multifarious requirements of clinical care, including the diagnosis and prognosis of disease, and thus facilitate a more profound comprehension of the biological processes involved. This has led to a surge in studies focusing on the identification of novel biomarkers in different pathologies such as multiple sclerosis (MS) (1).

MS is an immune-mediated disorder that affects the central nervous system. The clinical progression and response to treatment of this condition are highly heterogeneous, and the current diagnosis is based mainly on a combination of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans and lumbar punctures. However, these techniques do not accurately assess the complexity of the pathology, which makes it an ideal candidate for the study of new biomarkers that can help to diagnose and evaluate its evolution (2,3).

In this context, Vasoactive Intestinal Peptide (VIP) is presented as a possible candidate biomarker for this pathology. VIP is a neuropeptide with anti-inflammatory and neuromodulatory abilities that can affect the central nervous system (4). It has been demonstrated in earlier investigations employing mouse models of MS that VIP is capable of functioning as an immunomodulator and neuroprotector (5). Furthermore, the potential of this neuropeptide as a biomarker in various immune-mediated musculoskeletal pathologies, such as early arthritis and spondyloarthritis, has been investigated (6).

The objective of this article is to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of research on VIP as a potential biomarker in multiple sclerosis.

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2. Research question(s)

2.1. Primary research question(s)

Our research question is:

Can VIP be used as a diagnostic or prognostic biomarker in Multiple Sclerosis?

To answer this question, we will follow the PICO framework:

Population: Patients with Multiple Sclerosis

Intervention: Vasoactive Intestinal Peptide measurement

Outcome: Clinical markers (flares), radiological markers, markers of acute inflammation, markers of neurodegeneration.

3. Review team and other contributors

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ACM, YJM, IGC and CMM will participate in the conceptualization, investigation, screening, data curation and writing of the manuscript. All authors will read and approve the final manuscript.

4. Type of review

This is a systematic review

5. Search strategy

5.1. Databases

Three databases will be used to conduct the bibliographic search. The search engine PubMed will be used as a more general search engine, Embase as a database focused on biomedical research, and Cochrane as a healthcare database with a large representation of clinical studies.

5.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

This review will include any study performed with patients diagnosed with multiple sclerosis.

The selection of articles will be made exclusively from those published in indexed scientific journals. The following exclusion criteria will be used to filter articles for final selection: review

articles and articles based on animal models and *in vitro* research will not be selected. Studies lacking a clinical outcome, those not focusing on multiple sclerosis, and those not published in English, will also be excluded from this review.

5.3. Search strings or queries

In order to answer the research question proposed, the main concepts that will appear in the search are Vasoactive Intestinal Peptide and Multiple Sclerosis, along with any synonyms that may be related.

The query for each database is:

- **PubMed:** (("Multiple Sclerosis"[Mesh]) OR (multiple sclerosis[Title/Abstract])) AND (((("aviptadil" [Supplementary Concept]) OR (aviptadil[Title/Abstract])) OR ((N[Text Word] AND hexanoyl[Text Word] AND vasoactive[Text Word] AND intestinal[Text Word] AND polypeptide[Text Word]))) OR (("Vasoactive Intestinal Peptide"[Mesh]) OR (vasoactive[Title/Abstract] AND intestinal[Title/Abstract] AND peptide[Title/Abstract])))
- **Embase:** (('multiple sclerosis'/exp AND [embase]/lim) OR ('multiple sclerosis' AND [embase]/lim)) AND (((('vasoactive intestinal polypeptide' AND [embase]/lim) OR ('vasoactive intestinal polypeptide'/exp AND [embase]/lim)) OR (('aviptadil'/exp AND [embase]/lim) OR ('aviptadil' AND [embase]/lim)) OR ((n AND hexanoyl AND vasoactive AND intestinal AND [embase]/lim) AND (('polypeptide'/exp AND [embase]/lim) OR ('polypeptide' AND [embase]/lim))))
- **Cochrane:** (("Multiple Sclerosis"[Mesh]) OR (multiple sclerosis[Title/Abstract])) AND (((("aviptadil" [Supplementary Concept]) OR (aviptadil[Title/Abstract])) OR ((N[Text Word] AND hexanoyl[Text Word] AND vasoactive[Text Word] AND intestinal[Text Word] AND polypeptide[Text Word]))) OR (("Vasoactive Intestinal Peptide"[Mesh]) OR (vasoactive[Title/Abstract] AND intestinal[Title/Abstract] AND peptide[Title/Abstract])))

5.4. Search strategy justification

In the context of this search, the use of alternative terms for multiple sclerosis has been limited due to the lack of alternative disease denominations, avoiding the introduction of other less specific terms that could result in the unintentional introduction of unwanted pathologies. Furthermore, only those VIP synonyms that added value to the search have been incorporated; those that are rarely used or unrelated to the topic have been excluded.

6. Screening

6.1. Screening stages

Once the search has been carried out in the bibliographic databases, the results will be filtered in different stages, each one carried out in pairs and using EndNote (EndNote X9, 2013, Clarivate Analytics) as the bibliographic management tool.

Firstly, duplicate publications will be filtered out using a tool available in the bibliographic manager itself. Next, an initial filtering will be carried out based on the title and abstract of each publication, where the authors, journal and year of publication will also be available. If there are any disagreements among the reviewers regarding the suitability of an article in this first round, it will move on to the next selection phase.

In the second phase, publications will be selected after reading the full article. The publications selected at this stage will be used for the review.

All four members participating in the review will take part in this process.

6.2. Screening tool(s)

The following software tools will be utilised in order to carry out the work: the designated bibliographic manager will be Endnote, while Microsoft Excel will be utilised as a tool to consolidate the results. The work will be carried out in the OneDrive cloud.

6.3. Screener instructions

All selectors will receive a list of exclusion criteria. In the first phase, if there is any doubt about an article, it will be passed on to the next phase for more detailed review. If there is any doubt in the second phase, this will be shared with the other selectors, and they will discuss whether the article should be selected.

7. Data extraction

7.1. Data items

Data extracted from each included study will comprise study metadata (authors, year of publication and country), methodological characteristics (sample size, age and percentage of female participants), and sample characteristics (origin and the method follow to obtain it). Finally, data on VIP levels will be collected. Main findings will be summarized narratively.

7.2. Extraction stages

Data will be extracted by two extractors working on parallel, follow by a verification process. Once all the data is collected, it will be summarized in tables. All four members will participate in this stage.

7.3. Extraction tool(s)

Extraction will be performed using Microsoft Word and Excel as the main tools, always working from a file store in the OneDrive cloud.

8. Risk of bias (quality) assessment

For this review, quality assessment will be conducted using the Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies-2 (QUADAS-2). This tool allows the quality of articles selected for study to be assessed by evaluating four main areas: patient selection, index test, reference standard, and workflow and time. In order to conduct a more personalised study of the selected articles, a question was added to the index test section, which allows for improved analysis.

9. Synthesis

9.1. Missing or unclear data

If any article is found to be lacking relevant information for this review, or if the information provided is unclear, the corresponding author of the publication will be contacted via e-mail.

9.2. Synthesis method

The data extracted from the selected articles will be synthesized and a quantitative analysis will be done to conclude with a meta-analysis. If the heterogeneity of methodologies and outcomes does not allow for a quantitative meta-analysis, a qualitative approach will be done. Key results and methodological details will be organised and presented in summary tables to facilitate comparison between studies and highlight shared patterns and knowledge gaps.

9.3. Synthesis procedure

In the course of synthesising the information, the methodology employed in each of the studies will be analysed regarding both the diagnosis and the sample used to measure the marker. In addition, the results obtained will be subjected to thorough analysis, with the objective of producing a comprehensive summary.

10. Additional information

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